

THE LEVEL OF STUDY OF MOTIVATION AND MOTIVATION AS A PROBLEM

Amirova Nazokat O'roq qizi

Master of the 2nd year of the National University of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6161148>

Annotation: This article discusses the extent to which the problem of motive and motivation has been studied in world psychology.

Keywords: Motive, motivation, broad interpretation of motivation, needs, activities.

Motive is a force that motivates a person to act, a set of needs. The concept of motive has been defined by scientists as follows. According to Maslow, the motive is the sum of needs. SL Rubnstein "Motivation is the determination that takes place through the psyche."

A.N. Leontiv considers motives as thematic needs directed to human activity and vocabulary that motivates it. Motivation is a motivating factor for activities related to satisfying certain needs. Motivation in the broadest sense is considered to be a character of human activity, a complex multifaceted manager of his activity. Motivation is a set of reasons that motivate a person to be active. V.S. Merlin elaborated on some aspects of motive systems in more detail. He describes the process of formation of the system of motives as follows: "Different motives gradually become interconnected and interdependent, and ultimately form a unified system of motives." According to V.S. Merlin, the process of formation of the system of motives requires the fulfillment of conditions such as not only the stability of motives, but also the understanding of motives. SL Rubinstein makes the following comments on the psychological nature of motive: motivation is a determinant formed by the psyche; motive is a subjective reflection of a person's cognitive process of behavior that directly connects them to the outside world. We believe that a person is inextricably linked with being through his motives. Motives, which are manifested as the driving force of human behavior (behavior), play a leading role in the structure (composition) of the person. The structural structure of a motive includes a person's orientation, character, emotional state (ability), abilities, inner experiences, activities, and cognitive processes. Theoretical data collected in the field of psychology also show that a number of psychologists believe that character is the basis of the dynamic aspects of personality motives.

Well-known psychologist A.N. Through his monograph "Activity, Consciousness, Personality," Leontev introduced the theory of a new approach to the interpretation of motivation into science, which serves to theoretically substantiate the manifestation of the combination of motivation and attitude in the activities of the individual. So, A.N. Through. The existence of a psychological balance between personality, activity, consciousness and social activity in Leontev's interpretation plays an important methodological role in the creation of psychological mechanisms of the system of personal relations.

By linking the process of motivation of professional activity to the functional psychological model of the system of activity by V.D. Shadrikov, the motivation of the activity approach reveals the specific social and psychological prospects of vocational training to

some extent. Although motive is broadly defined as a behavioral determinant, many foreign researchers interpret personality motives in a very narrow sense and examine it scientifically, even though they do not include the amount of unconditional reflex acts, affective, stress, and expressive reactions in the motive system. A number of psychologists compare the energetic, spiritual, and spiritual aspects of a motive, interpreting the motive as a source of purely energetic bioenergetic activity, and interpreting it in a unique way without taking into account its spiritual and spiritual aspects. they strive. In particular, Z. Freud interprets the law of motive only as a dynamic energy state. According to a group of foreign psychologists, motive is the energetic aspect of experience and reactions (we will express criticism of the authors in another section of the study, as the attitude to this definition is very controversial).

Former Soviet psychologists interpret motives based on a combination of dynamic and spiritual (spiritual) homonyms in explaining and defining its components.

P.M. Jacobsan is one of the scholars who has extensively studied the problem of motives. The author summarizes in his monograph the study of the problem of motives in Russian psychology and abroad, the views on the various views in it. At the same time, it is important to expand the scope of research in this area by analyzing the relationship between the main characteristics of the individual and the issue of motivation in the context of motivation. B.A. Frolov divides motivation into subject-content, personal and social types. Emphasizes that they are conditioned by the subject matter of the activity. It is said that their interests, aspirations and needs are intertwined. It is also noted that motivation is related to social factors that affect personality and performance.

S.L. Rubinstein makes the following comments on the psychological nature of motive: motivation is a determinant formed by the psyche; motive is a subjective reflection of the cognitive process of a person's behavior that directly connects him with the outside world. We believe that a person is inextricably linked with being through his motives. Motives, which are manifested as the driving force of human behavior (behavior), play a leading role in the structure (composition) of the person. The structural structure of a motive includes a person's orientation, character, emotional state (ability), abilities, inner experiences, activities, and cognitive processes. Theoretical data collected in the field of psychology also show that a number of psychologists believe that character is the basis of the dynamic aspects of personality motives. In particular, while one or another quality of character forms purely dynamic characteristics, the rest create not only its dynamic nature, but also its spiritual and spiritual aspects. Motives are also related to emotions, which are not outside the nature of behavior, but are inextricably linked with the system of emotional experiences, motivational factors. One of the most important functions of emotion is that it serves to determine how important the moments that are important to a person are for him.

List of literature:

1. Goziev.E.G. "Methodological problems in psychological science" Shymkent. 2005
2. Leontiev.A.A."The psychology of sheathing" 1997
3. A.V.Petrovsky "General Psychology". 1992y.
4. www.arxiv.uz the

5. [edit]referen

